

Effective Teaching Modality in Conducting Hospitality Management Laboratory Courses: Basis for Skill Competencies

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Abstract: COVID-19 pandemic forced the Education Industry to suspend face-to-face classes and opt for alternative teaching modalities to prevent the spread of the virus. On account of this, students were forced to study and attend classes virtually from their homes. However, some courses in tertiary education like Hospitality Management—a skill-based course—require frequent laboratory works. The sudden switch of learning modality poses a huge challenge for the students and their opportunity to acquire and improve their skill competencies. Therefore, the researchers intend to evaluate the effectiveness of using the New Teaching Modalities in conducting Hospitality Management laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies based on the students' experience. This study was conducted using a quantitative design and the sample was taken using a Purposive sampling method. The 4th and 3rd-year students of Hospitality Management from De La Salle University-Dasmariñas are the respondents. A total of 91 respondents responded to the online survey that was distributed by the researchers through Facebook Messenger's private messaging and group chats. The Teaching Modalities—Online, Blended, and Face-to-Face—were evaluated by the students for the researchers to find out which among the three is the most effective. At the end of this study, results revealed that Face-to-Face is the most effective Teaching Modality in conducting HM laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies. Results showed that there is a significant difference between the Teaching Modalities in terms of the student's experience with the (1) Learning Practices used in the HM Laboratory Courses for Each Type of Teaching Modality, (2) Student's Class Involvement and Effort in Each Type of Teaching Modality, and (3) Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies during Each Type of Teaching Modality.

Keywords: Teaching Modality, Online, Blended, Face-to-face, Skill Competency, Pandemic.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this new modern era, technology has evolved and become widely used by everyone in various ways like in Education. With the development of technology throughout the years, Education also developed and incorporated technology to enhance learning, may it be through the use of a mobile phone, tablet, laptop, computer, etc. In a recent study by Dabbagh, Fake, and Zhang (2019), about “Student Perspectives of Technology use for Learning in Higher Education”, studies show that students recognized that technology was effective in developing discussion, collaboration, and interaction.

In the year 2020, the world has been disrupted by Covid-19 — an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus, which can be easily transmitted from person to person through droplets from coughing or sneezing, touching contaminated surfaces, and then touching your eyes, nose or mouth (WHO, 2020). This virus affected many countries around the world and this forced most countries to apply quarantine measures that limit transportation, seize the operation

of most Industries and suspend Education. The suspension pushed many schools to make alternative Teaching Modalities like fully switching to online learning. This sudden transition of learning mode has led to difficulties for Laboratory Courses. The graduates of such programs will have a key part in the recovery of the economy. It is possible to provide their required practical training in such programs through distance learning but it will require special arrangements (Daniel, 2020).

The Philippines announced its first locally transmitted case of Covid-19 on March 7, 2020, when most Universities/Colleges are halfway through their 2nd semester. Immediately, the government implemented quarantine policies including school suspensions. According to Commission on Higher Education (CHED) chair Prospero de Vera III (as cited in Montemayor, 2020) they encourage the use of online learning systems to make sure that the Higher Education Institution (HEI) students can continue learning amid the Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ).

Even before the ECQ, Higher Education Institutions like De La Salle University-Dasmariñas, have already been implementing blended learning with the use of technology mixed with traditional methods in education. This is widely used even in skill-based courses like Hospitality Management, allowing the instructors to give written assignments and assessments online. In the environment of online teaching and learning, the quality course design impacts the quality of teaching (Crews and Wilkinson, 2015). But online learning and face-to-face learning are different especially when it comes to Hospitality Management Course wherein the students' skills are the basis of a passing grade. With face-to-face learning, judging the students' level of understanding of materials from non-verbal behavior is possible for the professors and it also allows adjustments of instructions. To prevent misunderstandings, answering questions quickly is possible to provide clarifications (Kauffman, 2015).

For the students of Hospitality Management, a skill-based course with frequent laboratory work, this will be a big challenge as it may affect their skill competencies. It is in this context that the study will be undertaken.

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of using the New Teaching Modalities in conducting Hospitality Management laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies in terms of the students' experience.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework (Figure 1) is adapted from the Different Modalities of Instruction by McGovern, G. (2004). This study deals with the process of the different teaching modalities with different ways of how the students will receive the academic content in their schools using the internet, blended and face-to-face classes. Sipes and Ricciardi (2006) concluded that there are differences between online classes and face-to-face education that traditional courses are instructor-centered while the online courses are student-centered, which means that the traditional courses or traditional learning are the functions of the teacher is to the role the room lecturer and presents the lesson in the front with direct classroom discussion, the online learning is student-centered learning because the teacher will always do their roles by facilitator but the students do much more things like the activities to embrace their own online learning. (Lathan, n.d).

The framework explains that contexts in the school like the lessons and activities will go through the middle circles that show different processes in the way that the students will receive them clearly, the online, hybrid or blended, and face to face. Lastly, the main participants that will receive all of this process are the students. The nature of online and face-to-face education concluded that the main difference is that online instruction is student-centered while traditional courses are instructor-centered. Tutty and Kleine (2008) state that working with both the process of Online and Face-to-face collaboration affects a huge development learning strategy. While Cragg, Dunning, and Ellis (2008) found that there was no difference in the output of the two different modalities.

Theoretical Framework

Fig. 1. Different Modalities of Instruction by McGovern, G. (2004).

The researchers adapted McGovern's framework (2004) and modified it to suit the current study (Figure 2). The purpose of this framework is to understand how variables in this study connect. Wherein, it will show what type of Teaching Modality the 3rd year and 4th year students of DLSUD Hospitality Management is effective in Conducting Laboratory Courses in acquiring skill competencies.

First, the content will be the laboratory courses that the students will take in the 2021 – 2022 academic year. It contains the different lessons and performances that will be accomplished by the 3rd and 4th-year students of the DLSU-D Hospitality Management course. In the framework, there are different modalities of Instruction for McGovern (2004). The middle circles are the ways in which the students will receive the lessons; hence the Teaching Modalities are Online, Hybrid or Blended, and Face-to-Face. Lastly, the respondents that will evaluate the given Teaching Modalities are the students. This will show whether the Teaching Modalities are effective in conducting laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies for the HM students.

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 2. Conceptual Framework

Online classes or E-learning benefits the students and the teachers by saving time, it is convenient and flexible to use by the conductors, advance information that will help us on gaining knowledge, several multimedia's with rich and various contents and of course it avoids physical interactions of the people that may save us from the spreading virus. (Bates, 2005; Rosenberg, 2001). According to Sung (2010), A few analyses are curious and give attention to online classes and whether they will be effective in learning Hospitality Courses.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The researchers aim to determine which teaching modality will be effective in conducting HM laboratory courses in terms of the students' experience. Specifically, it is hoped that this study will answer the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of?
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Year Level
 - 1.4 Student Type
2. How effective are the teaching modalities in conducting HM laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies based on the student's experience in terms of:
 - 2.1 Learning Practices used in the HM Laboratory Courses for Each Type of Teaching Modality.
 - 2.2 Student's Class Involvement and Effort in Each Type of Teaching Modality
 - 2.3 Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies during Each Type of Teaching Modality
3. Is there a significant difference between the teaching modalities in terms of the student's experience on:
 - 3.1 Learning Practices used in the HM Laboratory Courses for Each Type of Teaching Modality.

3.2 Student's Class Involvement and Effort in Each Type of Teaching Modality

3.3 Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies during Each Type of Teaching Modality

4. Propose the most effective teaching modality in conducting HM laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies.

Hypothesis

- Online teaching modality (Synchronous and Asynchronous) is effective in conducting Hospitality Management laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies.
- Blended teaching modality (Hybrid or Combination of Face to face and online meetings) is effective in conducting Hospitality Management laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies.
- Face to Face teaching modality (Traditional) is effective in conducting Hospitality Management laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies.

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the Teaching Modalities in terms of the student's experience on (1) Learning Practices used in the HM Laboratory Courses for Each Type of Teaching Modality, (2) Student's Class Involvement and Effort in Each Type of Teaching Modality, and (3) Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies during Each Type of Teaching Modality.

IV. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Online (Synchronous and Asynchronous)

One of the greatest benefits of the internet is the online learning method that poses unexpected challenges to students prior to providing versatility and convenience (Brunvand & Byrd, 2011). Nowadays, the well-established concept of learning quality will give the students assurance and enhancement that the higher education institutions are coping up and practicing through the online community (Elassy, 2015).

Studies by Richardson and North (2020), about "Transition and Migration to Online Learning Environment" shows that despite the faculty's being unfamiliar with the use of online teaching, they were pleased with the process. Additionally, students were also pleased with the online transition.

Mobile devices are gaining popularity nowadays since it is easy to use, and technology is one of the fast and most significant contact media. Educators consider the smartphone as an alternative to modern teaching since the usage of smartphones is rapidly growing. (Sawsan & Qassim, 2020).

Studies by Pinto-Llorente, Sánchez-Gómez, García-Peñalvo, and Casillas-Martín (2017) about "Students' perceptions and attitudes towards asynchronous technological tools in blended-learning training to improve grammatical competence in English as a second language", showed the students perception wherein they highlighted the opportunities of asynchronous technological tools which provided to have more prominent independence for them to be able to set and organize their own pace of study and individual learning.

According to Baker & Unni (2018), there are no significant differences in terms of effectiveness between online learning and traditional learning. Online learning can be defined as pure no face-to-face learning all the communication and school work can be done online.

Blended (Hybrid or Combination of Face to face meetings)

The Higher Education Institution evolved some strategies for teaching strategies like e-learning, distance learning, mobile learning, etc., by using teaching technology, the concept of blended learning is a combination of face-to-face teaching and online learning. The advantage of blended learning is that it can access a wide range of participants. (Sinan & Halil, 2019)

The educators are interested in blended learning since they can use online learning and face-to-face learning in teaching. The students can be more flexible in blended learning since distance will never be a barrier for the student to participate in classroom activities. (Ahmad, Kardoyo, Henky, et al, 2020)

Face-to-Face (Traditional)

According to Norman, C. & Molly, B. (2010) the responses from faculty and students, there are more positive experiences on face to face meetings since there is more personal communication between the student and the instructor, the responsiveness and concern from the instructors were lacking in online learning.

As the battle of Covid-19 pandemic goes on in the Philippines, Senator Christopher Lawrence Bong Go said "They (students) cannot stop their studies, schools must also prepare their facilities and lay down protocols in preparation for the possible scenarios that students, teachers, and education personnel will face when classes resume." (Al Bawaba, 2020)

With the previous research and statements about online learning and teaching modalities, it is hoped that with this study, the researchers will be able to fill the gap by determining which teaching modality will be effective in conducting hospitality management laboratory courses in order to help HM students of DLSUD-CTHM to acquire skill competencies during this time of the covid-19 pandemic.

V. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quantitative research design was used to conduct this study. Quantitative research design allows the researchers to gather the data in numerical form that will be measured in different graphs and tables. It deals with numbers to access information; it is also possible to summarize, compare, or generalize the findings. (Goertzen, 2017). It enabled the researchers to gather more accurate data and statistical information using online surveys. Specifically, this design was able to provide the researchers with a generalizable conclusion at the end of this study with honest answers from the respondents.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at De La Salle University-Dasmarinas, Cavite. Researchers specifically chose to conduct this study on Hospitality Management students of the College of Tourism and Hospitality Management (CTHM).

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the 3rd year and 4th year Hospitality Management students who experienced laboratory subjects in different teaching modalities from online, blended, and traditional face-to-face. The number of student's population are as follows:

- 3rd Year - 74 students
- 4th Year - 100 students

Total of 174 student respondents.

Sampling Method

The researchers used the Purposive Sampling Method as their sample method wherein it is an intentional choice of informants based on their capacity to clarify a particular subject, idea, or phenomenon (Robinson, 2014). The researchers chose the purposive sampling method since there is a specific target of individuals who will fit as their participants.

Research Instrument

The researchers provided online surveys using google forms and distributed them to the respondents via Facebook Messenger to gather the needed data from the Hospitality Management students. The online survey will be based on the researchers' objectives and statements of the problems. Respondents were asked to evaluate the effectiveness of the Teaching Modalities using the Likert scaling method, a rating system intended to measure individuals' attitudes, opinions, or perceptions (Jamieson, 2017).

Data Gathering Procedure

The online survey was distributed to the Hospitality Management students in the 2nd semester of the school year 2021-2022. Google Forms was used to conduct this online survey and was distributed to the respondents online. Researchers gathered enough data and information about the effectiveness of the New Teaching Modalities in the laboratory courses for Hospitality Management students. With the use of Google Forms, the researchers were able to collect and save the responses online automatically.

Data Treatment and Analysis

The collected data from the online surveys were analyzed using frequency, mean, and ANOVA (Fisher, 1918). Statistical Treatment of the data and information gathered was treated in the following manner:

1. Frequency counts and percentages were used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents.
2. Ranking was utilized to ascertain the order of effective teaching modality in conducting laboratory courses using the Likert Scaling Method.
3. The weighted mean is similar to an arithmetic mean (the most common type of average), where instead of each of the data points contributing equally to the final average, some data points contribute more than others. The notion of weighted mean plays a role in descriptive statistics and also occurs in a more general form in several other areas of mathematics. This was used to answer the question on the assessment of the difference between and among the teaching modalities in the effectiveness of conducting laboratory courses in HM programs as a basis for acquiring skill competencies.

To interpret the data, a 5-Point Likert Scale was used. The table below shows the point interval and its interpretation.

Table 1: 5-Point Likert Scale Point Interval and Interpretation

Interval	Level of Agreement/ Disagreement	Level of Effectiveness
1.0 – 1.49	Strongly disagree	Not at all Effective
1.5 – 2.49	Disagree	Slightly Effective
2.5 – 3.49	Neutral	Moderately effective
3.5 – 4.49	Agree	Very Effective
4.5 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Extremely Effective

4. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) repeated measure was used to test for significant differences between and among the three teaching modalities in the effectiveness of conducting laboratory courses in HM programs as a basis for acquiring skill competencies. Likewise, it tested the hypothesis that the means among two or more groups are equal, under the assumption that the sampled populations are normally distributed. This was used in the computation of the hypothesis.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section shows the results and discussions of the survey conducted by the researchers. A total of 91 Hospitality Management students responded to the study's survey entitled “Effective Teaching Modality in Conducting Hospitality Management Laboratory Courses: Basis for Skill Competencies.”

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of?

1.1 Age

Table 2: Respondent’s Age Frequency and Percentage Distribution

Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
19-20	9	9.9	9.9	9.9
21-22	62	68.1	68.1	78.0
23-24	19	20.9	20.9	98.9
27	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
Total	91	100.0	100.0	

The table shows the frequency distribution of the age of the respondents. Based on table 1.1, out of the 91 respondents, the highest percentage, 68.1%, belongs to ages 21-22. The second to the highest percentage are ages 23-24 years old with 20.9%. The second to the lowest is the 19-20 years old with the percentage of 9.9%. Lastly, there was only one respondent at 27 years old and got the 1.1% which is also the lowest.

1.2 Gender

Table 3: Respondent’s Gender Frequency and Percentage Distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	42	46.2	46.2	46.2
Male	49	53.8	53.8	100.0
Total	91	100.0	100.0	

As table 3 shows the gender of the respondents, out of 91 respondents, 53.8% are male and 46.2 % are female. Based on the results, most of the respondents are male.

According to Sax, Gilmartin & Bryant (2003) and; Smith & Leigh (1997), Men may respond to web-based surveys in more significant numbers than women, contrary to traditional surveys, according to specific examinations of the behavior of respondents to online surveys.

1.3 Year Level

Table 4: Respondent’s Year Level Frequency and Percentage Distribution

Year Level	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
3 rd year	41	45.1	45.1	45.1
4 th year	50	54.9	54.9	100.0
Total	91	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 shows that the highest number of respondents are the 4th-year student, at 54.9%. To be followed by 3rd-year students with a percentage of 45.1%.

1.4 Student Type

Table 5: Respondent’s Student Type Frequency and Percentage Distribution

Student Type	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Irregular	6	6.6	6.6	6.6
Regular	85	93.4	93.4	100.0
Total	91	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 reveals the frequency distribution of student types; out of 91 respondents, 85 students are regular students with a percentage of 93.4%, and 6 are irregular students with 6.6%.

Table 6: 5-Point Likert Scale Point Interval and Interpretation

Interval	Level of Agreement/ Disagreement	Level of Effectiveness
1.0 – 1.49	Strongly disagree	Not at all Effective
1.5 – 2.49	Disagree	Slightly Effective
2.5 – 3.49	Neutral	Moderately effective
3.5 – 4.49	Agree	Very Effective
4.5 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Extremely Effective

The table above shows the Likert scale point interval and interpretation that was used to interpret the next following table.

2. How effective are the teaching modalities in conducting HM laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies based on the student’s experience in terms of:

2.1 Learning Practices used in the HM Laboratory Courses for Each Type of Teaching Modality.

Table 7: Results interpretation on the Effectiveness of Learning Practices Used in the HM Laboratory Courses

Effectiveness of Learning Practices Used in the HM Laboratory Courses	TEACHING MODALITY								
	ONLINE			BLENDED			FACE-TO-FACE		
	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
1. Class lesson discussion.	3.36	1.15	Moderately Effective	3.96	0.82	Very Effective	4.71	0.58	Extremely Effective
2. Class demonstration.	3.28	1.16	Moderately Effective	3.91	0.96	Very Effective	4.69	0.66	Extremely Effective
3. Self-practice (Self-directed learning).	3.30	1.24	Moderately Effective	3.75	0.94	Very Effective	4.48	0.91	Very Effective
4. Group/ Collaborative practice (Group-directed learning).	3.16	1.34	Moderately Effective	3.88	0.88	Very Effective	4.65	0.64	Extremely Effective
5. Individual performance task execution.	3.58	1.17	Very Effective	3.91	0.88	Very Effective	4.68	0.63	Extremely Effective
6. Group performance task execution.	3.11	1.33	Moderately Effective	4.01	0.86	Very Effective	4.65	0.64	Extremely Effective
Overall Mean	3.30	1.03	Moderately Effective	3.90	0.76	Very Effective	4.64	0.55	Extremely Effective

The table above implies the effectiveness of learning practices used in the HM Laboratory Courses during the different teaching modalities, which are Online, Blended, and Face-to-face. The respondents strongly agree that the face-to-face modality is extremely effective, with a mean of 4.64; the blended modality got the respondents' second choice with an overall mean of 3.90 and was interpreted as very effective. On the other hand, the lowest accumulated mean is the online modality, which is moderately effective, with a mean of 3.30.

Therefore, the results on this table show that face-to-face or traditional is an extremely effective way of learning teaching practices used in HM Laboratory Courses. Among the two other modalities, the respondents prefer the traditional face-to-face class inside a classroom or laboratory.

2.2 Student's Class Involvement and Effort in Each Type of Teaching Modality

Table 8: Results interpretation on the Student’s Class Involvement and Effort

Student's Class Involvement and Effort	TEACHING MODALITY								
	ONLINE			BLENDED			FACE-TO-FACE		
	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
1. I find the course subject challenging.	3.71	1.20	Agree	3.66	0.91	Agree	3.81	1.36	Agree
2. I am well prepared before each class (finished assignments, reviewed previous lessons, arrived at class early/on time, and assessed your understanding of the lessons)	3.07	1.23	Neutral	3.63	0.90	Agree	4.27	0.87	Agree
3. I actively participate during class discussions.	3.29	1.12	Neutral	3.77	0.87	Agree	4.18	1.00	Agree
4. I ask questions regarding the course subject.	3.14	1.23	Neutral	3.55	1.10	Agree	4.15	1.07	Agree
5. I am able to finish and submit all assigned assignments on time.	3.40	1.26	Neutral	3.90	0.93	Agree	4.44	0.86	Agree
6. I study in advance and put effort into the course subject.	3.03	1.19	Neutral	3.67	0.93	Agree	4.04	1.15	Agree
Overall Mean	3.27	0.95	Moderately Effective	3.70	0.71	Very Effective	4.15	0.80	Very Effective

Table 8 shows the interpretation of the results of the student’s class involvement and effort during Online, Blended, and Face-to-face teaching modalities. Among the three teaching modalities, Face-to-face teaching modality has the highest mean of 4.15 which interprets as Very Effective for the respondents. Next is the Blended teaching modality with a 3.70 mean that interprets as Very Effective as well. The Online teaching modality has the lowest overall mean with 3.27 that interprets as moderately effective for the respondents. Results in this table show that the respondents find the Face-to-Face teaching modality as the most effective among the other two teaching modalities—Blended and Online—as a tool for influencing their class involvement and efforts in their laboratory courses.

2.3 Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies during Each Type of Teaching Modality

Table 9: Results interpretation on the Student’s Improvement in Skill Competencies

<i>Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies</i>	TEACHING MODALITY								
	ONLINE			BLENDED			FACE-TO-FACE		
	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
1. My knowledge of the course subject increased.	3.27	1.12	Neutral	3.92	0.88	Agree	4.70	0.55	Strongly Agree
2. My laboratory skills in the course subject improved.	2.98	1.17	Neutral	3.85	0.93	Agree	4.78	0.49	Strongly Agree
3. My communication skills improved.	3.22	1.18	Neutral	3.87	0.85	Agree	4.65	0.69	Strongly Agree
4. My collaborative skills improved.	3.20	1.28	Neutral	3.82	0.84	Agree	4.64	0.59	Strongly Agree
5. My teamwork skills improved.	3.20	1.30	Neutral	3.85	0.88	Agree	4.68	0.56	Strongly Agree
6. My leadership skills improved.	3.18	1.41	Neutral	3.70	1.01	Agree	4.51	0.91	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.17	1.09	Moderately Effective	3.84	0.69	Very Effective	4.66	0.51	Extremely Effective

Table 9 shows the result and interpretation of the student’s Improvement in Skill competencies during Online, Blended, and Face-to-face. Face-to-face teaching Modality acquired the highest mean of 4.66, with a standard deviation of 0.51, the Interpretation is Extremely Effective. To be followed by the Blended Teaching Modality come by the mean of 3.84, with a standard deviation of 0.69 which interprets as Very Effective. Lastly, the Online Teaching Modality obtained the lowest mean of 3.17, with a standard deviation of 1.09 interpreted as Moderately Effective. Hence, the respondents agreed that the face-to-face teaching modality is Extremely Effective in Student’s Improvement in Skill Competencies.

For interpretation of the following table, if the significance value is less than the level of significance of 0.05, the decision would be to reject Ho. Reject Ho implies that there is a significant difference in the groups being compared.

3. Is there a significant difference between the teaching modalities in terms of the student's experience on:

3.1 Learning Practices used in the HM Laboratory Courses for Each Type of Teaching Modality.

Table 10: Significant Difference Between the Teaching Modality in terms of Learning Practices

Modality	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig	Decision	Interpretation
Online	3.299	1.028	0.000	reject Ho	there is a significant difference
Blended	3.903	0.760			
Face-to-face	4.645	0.548			

There is a significant difference between the teaching modalities—Online, Blended, and Face-to-Face—in terms of the Learning Practices used in the HM laboratory courses. The null hypothesis of ‘There is no significant difference between the Teaching Modalities in terms of the Learning Practices used in the HM laboratory courses’ is rejected. Based on table 10, Face-to-face teaching modality has the highest mean value of 4.645, compared to the other two teaching modalities wherein Blended has a mean value of 3.903 and Online has the lowest mean value of 3.299.

3.2 Student's Class Involvement and Effort in Each Type of Teaching Modality

Table 11: Significant Difference Between the Teaching Modality in terms of Student’s Class Involvement and Effort

Modality	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig	Decision	Interpretation
Online	3.273	0.945	0.000	reject Ho	there is a significant difference
Blended	3.696	0.714			
Face-to-face	4.150	0.795			

There is a significant difference between the teaching modalities—Online, Blended, and Face-to-Face—in terms of the Student’s Class Involvement and Effort. The null hypothesis of ‘There is no significant difference between the Teaching Modalities in terms of the Student’s Class Involvement and Effort’ is rejected. Based on table 11, Face-to-face teaching modality has the highest mean value of 4.150 compared to the other two teaching modalities wherein Blended has a mean value of 3.696 and Online has the lowest mean value of 3.273.

3.3 Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies during Each Type of Teaching Modality

Table 12: Significant Difference Between the Teaching Modality in terms of Student’s Improvement in Skill Competencies

Modality	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig	Decision	Interpretation
Online	3.174	1.092	0.000	reject Ho	there is a significant difference
Blended	3.835	0.695			
Face-to-face	4.659	0.508			

There is a significant difference between the teaching modalities—Online, Blended, and Face-to-Face—in terms of the Student’s Improvement in Skill Competencies. The null hypothesis of ‘There is no significant difference between the Teaching Modalities in terms of the Student’s Improvement in Skill Competencies’ is rejected. Based on table 12, Face-to-face teaching modality has the highest mean value of 4.659, compared to the other two teaching modalities wherein Blended has a mean value of 3.835 and Online has the lowest mean value of 3.174.

4. Propose the most effective teaching modality in conducting HM laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies.

Based on the results and findings from the respondent's answers to the online survey on the effectiveness of teaching modalities—Online, Blended, and Face-to-Face—, it shows that the Face-to-Face teaching modality has the highest overall mean value in each of the following factors that were used to rate the effectiveness of the 3 teaching modalities (Table 13), which means that Face-to-Face is the most effective teaching modality in conducting HM laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies.

Table 13: Overall Mean Comparison of the 3 Teaching Modalities

	TEACHING MODALITY					
	ONLINE		BLENDED		FACE TO FACE	
	Overall Mean	Interpretation	Overall Mean	Interpretation	Overall Mean	Interpretation
Learning Practices Used in the HM Laboratory Courses	3.30	Moderately Effective	3.90	Very Effective	4.64	Extremely Effective
Student’s Class Involvement and Effort	3.27	Moderately Effective	3.70	Very Effective	4.15	Very Effective
Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies	3.17	Moderately Effective	3.84	Very Effective	4.66	Extremely Effective

VII. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study focused on the effective teaching modality in conducting Hospitality Management Laboratory Courses: Basis for Skill Competencies. The results of this study must be interpreted with caution and a number of limitations should be borne in mind. There are two major limitations in this study that could be addressed in future research.

First, this study was based on the general experiences of the students with the different teaching modalities used to conduct their laboratory course subjects in their college years. Only the 3rd and 4th-year students were qualified to be the respondents for this study because they experienced the three different modalities due to the sudden switch from Face-to-face and Blended modality to Online modality caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in the middle of the school year. Second, there is no specific laboratory course subject that this study is based on to evaluate the effectiveness of the different teaching modalities in conducting HM laboratory courses. Arranging a setting where the students will be assigned to a specific laboratory course subject and be divided between the three teaching modalities, for them to experience and evaluate the teaching modalities in a given time frame is beyond the researcher's resources and capability, considering the pandemic situation.

Furthermore, there is a minor limitation that can be solved in future research as well. The number of respondents is the total population of the 3rd year (74) and 4th year (100) students of Hospitality Management, a total of 174 student respondents. However, upon data retrieval of the online survey, only 91 out of 174 students successfully responded. The researchers listed possible reasons for this, such as students being offline and not receiving the information about the online survey, ignoring the online survey, or lack of time due to a busy schedule.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study intends to evaluate the effectiveness of using the New Teaching Modalities in conducting Hospitality Management laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies in terms of the students' experience. Based on the result of this research, it can be concluded that:

Learning Practices used in the HM Laboratory Courses for Each Type of Teaching Modality.

Online

The online teaching modality is moderately effective in terms of Learning Practices in HM Laboratory Courses such as class lesson discussion, class demonstration, and group performance execution. The overall mean is 3.30, and the results show that respondents are more leaning toward the traditional class in terms of self-practices, group activities, and the like.

Blended

Blended Teaching Modality is very effective overall for the student respondents in terms of the Learning Practices used in the HM Laboratory Courses. Respondents agreed that the learning practices—Class lesson discussion, Class demonstration, Self-practice, Group/Collaborative practice, Individual performance task execution, and Group performance task execution—in a Blended Teaching setting are very effective for conducting HM laboratory courses. It means that the lessons and laboratory instructions are relayed effectively to the students and give them a clear understanding of the course subject and its laboratory tasks. In addition, it also allows the students to effectively practice and execute their laboratory performances in groups or individually.

Face-to-Face

The Face-to-face modality got the overall result of extremely effective Learning Practices Used in the HM Laboratory Courses. Respondents agreed that in terms of Class lesson discussion, Class demonstration, and Self-practice. Group/Collaborative practice, Individual performance task execution, and Group performance task execution are effective and found essential in performing group tasks and collaboration inside the laboratory. With a mean of 4.64. Unlike the online and blended modalities, Face-to-face is undoubtedly extremely effective for the 3rd and 4th year HM students.

Student's Class Involvement and Effort in Each Type of Teaching Modality

Online

Online Teaching Modality is Moderately Effective for the students in terms of their class involvement and effort in this teaching setting, with an overall mean value of 3.27. The respondents agreed that they find the course subject challenging during Online Teaching Modality. However, results show that it is not that challenging compared to Blended and Face-to-

face teaching modalities, with Online having a mean value of 3.71, Blended with a higher mean value of 3.66, and Face-to-face getting the highest mean value of 3.81. Aside from this, the respondent's responses are all neutral in terms of their preparedness, participation, task submissions, and advance studying. Unlike in Blended and Face-to-face Teaching Modality where the response is mostly to agree. This reveals that Online is the least effective Teaching Modality to affect students positively regarding their class involvement and effort compared to the Blended and Face-to-Face Teaching Modality.

Blended

Blended Teaching Modality is Very Effective for the students in terms of their class involvement and effort in this teaching setting, with an overall mean value of 3.70. The respondents agreed that they find the course subject challenging during Blended Teaching Modality, with a mean value of 3.66. A few decimals are greater than Online Teaching Modality, with a mean value of 3.71, but also a few decimals behind the Face-to-Face Teaching Modality, with a mean value of 3.81. In addition to this, the respondent's responses also agree in terms of their preparedness, participation, task submissions, and advance studying. Compared to Online and Face-to-face, Blended is a much more effective Teaching Modality to affect students positively regarding their class involvement and effort compared to Online Teaching Modality. However, Blended is a lesser effective Teaching modality compared to Face-to-Face.

Face-to-Face

Face-to-Face Teaching Modality is Very Effective for the students in terms of their class involvement and effort in this teaching setting. Respondents agree that they find Face-to-Face Teaching Modality as the most challenging for their course subject, with a mean value of 3.81, compared to Online, with a mean value of 3.71, and Blended, with a mean value of 3.66. Moreover, the respondents also agree that Face-to-Face Teaching Modality is the most effective when it comes to their preparedness, participation, task submissions, and advance studying. Compared to Online and Blended Teaching Modalities, Face-to-Face is the most effective Teaching Modality to affect students positively regarding their class involvement and effort.

Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies during Each Type of Teaching Modality

Online

In Accordance with the respondents, Online Teaching Modality has an overall mean of 3.17. It is clearly shown that the Online teaching modality is moderately effective in Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies compared to Blended and Face-to-face modalities. The online modality signifies the neutral response of the student's knowledge improvement, laboratory skills, communication skills, collaboration skills, teamwork skills, and leadership skills. Compared to the blended, that is an agreed very effective and Face-to-face, which is strongly agreed.

Blended

Blended Teaching Modality acquired a 3.84 overall mean which signifies Very Effective in Student's Improvement in Skill Competencies. The result of the survey showed that Blended Teaching Modality is Effective in Increasing knowledge in course subject, improvement of skills in the laboratory, improvement of communication skills, improvement of collaborative, teamwork, and leadership skills. Furthermore, the respondents agreed that the skills of the students can improve in Blended teaching Modality compared to Online Teaching Modality.

Face-to-Face

Face-to-Face Teaching Modality is extremely effective in Student's improvement in skill Competencies with a mean of 4.66, in face-to-face or traditional classes are vital in enhancing the skills of the students in the kitchen laboratory. With the addition of the student's and professors' presence and communication, the survey shows that the classes in face-to-face increased more in enhancing the skills. Therefore the respondents agreed that face-to-face is the most effective teaching modality in terms of Increasing knowledge of course subject, Improvement of skills in laboratory subject, improvement of Communication, collaborative, teamwork, and leadership skills. Based on the result there are significant differences between Online, Blended, and Face-to-face teaching modalities.

Significant Differences between the Teaching Modalities

There is a significant difference between the Teaching Modalities—Online, Blended, and Face-to-Face—in terms of the student's experience on the Learning Practices, Student's Class Involvement and Effort, and Student's Improvement in Skill

Competencies. The null hypothesis of 'There is no significant difference between the Teaching Modalities' is rejected. Results showed that Face-to-Face is the most effective Teaching Modality in conducting HM laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies.

The Hypothesis 'Online, Blended, and Face-to-face teaching modality are effective in conducting Hospitality Management laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies' is true. Apart from this, the results of this study revealed that Face-to-Face is the most effective teaching modality among the three for conducting HM laboratory courses as a basis for acquiring skill competencies.

IX. RECOMMENDATION

The study done for this thesis has shown several areas in which it would be helpful to future researchers. Based on the results and limitations of the study, it is recommended for future researchers to continue to expand and improve the analysis by changing the number of participants or education level as long as they experienced the different teaching modalities. Also, additional teaching modalities may be included in the study other than Online, Blended, and Face-to-face. Aside from this, they may narrow down into one specific laboratory course to acquire more accurate results as well as improve, enhance or add factors that can test the effectiveness of the different teaching modalities. Additionally, the research design may be changed, they may use qualitative research design, case study, group discussion, correlational study, and the like. Moreover, future researchers and others may carry out a different data collection method aside from online surveys like interviews and focus groups.

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